

THE WAYS OF OPTIMIZING THE ORGANIZATION OF SPEECH THERAPY ASSISTANCE FOR CHILDREN WITH SPEECH DISORDERS

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***Abstract.** The article clearly outlines the basic requirements for a developmental environment in a preschool organization and provides criteria for choosing materials and equipment to ensure the comprehensive development of children. The creation of a developing subject-spatial environment and recommendations in a preschool organization will ensure the development of various types of children's activities, taking into account the age characteristics of children. The article is addressed to directors, methodologists, teachers, psychologists of preschool educational institutions and parents on ways to optimize.*

***Keywords:** developmental, environment, speech, preschool organization, equipment, children, quality, speech therapy work, violation, optimization ways.*

A child's well-developed speech is an important condition for his overall development, for his socialization in society, and for successful learning at school. Speech disorders negatively affect all mental functions and affect the child's activity as a whole and his behavior. Therefore, the search for ways to optimize the organization of speech therapy assistance, as well as pedagogical interaction at different age stages and in different conditions, continues. In recent decades, foreign speech therapy has been developing intensively, innovative areas of correctional and pedagogical work are emerging, new methods of correcting speech disorders are being developed and implemented, and experts are discussing new factors that influence the success of speech therapy correction. Researchers have identified various ways to optimize the correctional pedagogical process aimed at overcoming speech disorders, including improving the quality of speech therapy work with children with speech disorders (T.B.Filicheva, G.V.Chirkina, etc.), improving professional skills speech therapists (improving the quality of speech therapy work with children with speech disorders (T.B.Filicheva, G.V.Chirkina, O.M.Vershinina, etc.). Speech therapy is considered as a pedagogical science based on general didactic and specific principles of searching and developing methods for differential diagnosis, correction and prevention of speech disorders. A systematic and comprehensive approach to the correction of speech disorders is of particular importance. And also at present, new topical problems of speech therapy and ways to solve them are being identified, trends in the development of speech therapy as a science are becoming clearer, clearly defined trends are being traced that have deep connections, on the one hand, with the origins of speech therapy in the 19th, 20th and 20th centuries. the current level of development of scientific fields related to speech therapy.

A comparative analysis and synthesis of available scientific data indicates that the success of speech therapy work depends not only on the degree of proficiency of a specialist in speech therapy technologies, but also on whether he can adequately assess his own professional activities and properly interact with other participants in the correctional process.

The study of current issues of speech pathology and its correction is impossible without the connection of speech therapy with other sciences and especially with psychology, neuropsychology, and psycholinguistics. Particular importance is attached to the works of (T.B.Filicheva, G.V.Chirkina, O.M.Vershina). The features of this kind of interaction are studied by many researchers. The interaction of a speech therapist with a family with a speech disorder was studied in the works of B.M.Grinspun, R.E.Levina, O.V.Pravdina, O.A.Tokareva, M.E.Khvattseva, Yu.F.Garkushi, L.R.Davidovich, T.S.Reznichenko, etc. Researchers are developing forms of joint work of speech therapists and families raising a child with speech impairment (Yu.F.Garkusha, T.Danilina, Yu.P.Dokuchaeva, O.L.Zvereva, N.Mishina, V.V.Yurtaikin, etc.). Other authors reveal certain aspects professional relations between the speech therapist and other specialists: speech therapist and doctors involved in the correction of speech disorders (L.I.Belyakova, T.G.Vizel, E.V.Lavrova, E.M.Mastyukova, Shokhor-Trotskaya, etc.); speech therapist and teachers, psychologists of preschool and school educational institutions (S.N.Shakhovskaya, V.I.Seliverstov, S.N.Sazonova, N.L.Krylova, L.N.Efimenkova, I.N.Sadovnikova, etc.).

According to information available in the specialized literature, sound pronunciation defects in children accounted for more than 17% (data from M.E.Khvattsev in the 50s). V.M. Grinspun gives such indicators as 25-30% among preschoolers 5-6 years old, 17-20% among schoolchildren in grades 1-2 and 1% of high school students. Modern authors provide much more accurate data. For example, the speech therapy textbook (2004) notes 52.5% of violations of sound pronunciation in children. Research by T.B. Filicheva indicates that the number of preschool children with speech underdevelopment is 40-50%. She studied 5128 preschool children, and 948 of them had general underdevelopment of speech. T.B. Filicheva identified the 4th level of OHP in 1749 children - phonetic-phonemic underdevelopment of speech and other speech pathologies. Among the severe speech disorders, and the most common, is dysarthria. Dysarthria is a severe speech disorder, which, as a speech pathology, is studied and covered in theoretical and practical aspects. All modern authors believe that the study of dysarthria should include neurological, psychological and speech therapy areas. At the present stage of development of special pedagogy, speech therapy is an interdisciplinary field that includes medical knowledge, neuropsychology, logopsychology, pedagogical, and rehabilitation aspects. In the specialized literature, dysarthria in childhood is considered as a residual phenomenon of cerebral palsy. Recently, the term "erased dysarthria" has appeared, which is diagnosed in children with minimal neurological signs. The problems of dysarthria were considered from a medical aspect by E.N.Vinarskaya, A.M.Pulatov, L.I.Belyakova's clinical and psychological features in children with dysarthria are described in Russian literature (E.N.Vinarskaya, L.O.Badalyan, E.M.Mastyukova, L.T.Zhurba, L.N.Lopatina, etc.)¹, pedagogical - L.V.Lopatina, I.I.Mamaichuk, O.G.Prihodko, V.I.Ippolitova, etc. Clinical forms of speech disorders in cerebral palsy (CP) are extremely diverse. The most common clinical form of speech disorders in cerebral palsy (from 65 to 85% of cases) are various variants of dysarthria (M.B.Eidinova, E.N.Pravdina-Vinarskaya; E.M.Mastyukova). Nosological and topical differential diagnosis of forms of dysarthria is usually carried out based on the totality of accompanying neurological symptoms (this point was emphasized, for example, by M.S.Margulis). The clinical approach examines the causes of dysarthria, the topic and nature of the focal lesion of the central nervous system, and symptoms. The presence of dysarthria is

associated with organic or functional damage to the brain, which in turn is caused by a variety of harmful factors that can affect the body at different periods of its development. All this generally indicates a trend towards an increase in speech pathology.

According to clinical and psychological characteristics, children with dysarthria can be conditionally divided into several groups depending on their general psychophysical development: dysarthria in children with normal psychophysical development; dysarthria in children with cerebral palsy; dysarthria in children with mental retardation; dysarthria in children with hydrocephalus; dysarthria in children with mental retardation; dysarthria in children with minimal brain dysfunction.

The authors note that children with dysarthria are characterized by impaired intellectual activity: impaired memory, attention, and performance. As a rule, such children have a low level of understanding of verbal instructions, insufficiency of the regulatory function of speech, a low level of control over their own activities, impaired cognitive activity, and low mental performance due to instability of the mental state. The term “dysarthria” refers to a disorder of the pronunciation side of speech, in which sound pronunciation and prosodic organization of the sound flow are disrupted. Regardless of the level of damage to the central nervous system, dysarthria affects the integrity of the functional system of expressive speech production. In this case, the pitch, tone, volume of the voice, the rhythmic and intonation level of the utterance are disrupted, the phonetic coloring of speech sounds is distorted, and in general the phonetic structure of speech is incorrectly realized. This pathology of articulate speech is associated mainly with a violation of the innervation of the muscles of the peripheral speech apparatus, due to which a disorder of muscle tone occurs as a result of organic or functional damage to the central nervous system. (E.F.Arkipova) Currently, there are 4 main approaches to the study dysarthria: clinical (neurological), linguistic, neuropsychological and psychological-pedagogical.

This formulation of the issue is especially important for Uzbekistan, where there is an even more significant increase in speech pathology with a small number of speech pathologists (on average from 10% to 17% in Russia, and about 0.6% - 10% in Uzbekistan according to the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation and RUz.). However, these studies do not currently solve the problem of studying and corrective-developmental education and upbringing of children with severe speech impairments, especially children with dysarthria. Despite the abundance of scientific domestic and foreign (mainly Russian) works devoted to the problems of speech disorders in different categories of children, the correctional and pedagogical process in specialized preschool institutions, the results of these studies do not reach our regions. And also due to the lack of speech therapists, and if there are specialists, then due to lack of knowledge of the Russian language, foreign experience is not sufficiently generalized. In this regard, we believe that it is necessary to systematize and generalize the existing foreign experience on this problem in the native language and bring it to practitioners - speech therapists. Speech therapists have to understand the structure of severe speech disorders on their own. Having mastered the basics of neuropathology and phonetics, a speech therapist will be able to freely cope with the diagnosis of developmental disorders, including speech disorders. And also with the choice of pathogenetically determined optimal forms of its correction. Since focal brain lesions are very diverse, for example, dysarthric children may have complex combinations of speech. Motor, cognitive disorders. In order to understand dysarthria well, a speech therapist must know dyslalia, alalia, aphasia, stuttering, and various types of delays in speech and mental development, and speech disorders in

deafness and hearing loss, and in mental retardation. It is important for a speech therapist to know and identify that: the listed speech disorders develop after the completion of speech formation in a child, then they manifest themselves only as dysarthria, but if speech development is not yet completed, then dysarthria becomes the basis for systemic delays in the development of perception and understanding of speech and skills reading and writing, as well as the general mental development of the child. Various systemic speech and mental disorders are often combined with pedagogical neglect of the child. This “bouquet” of various factors aggravates the difficulties of child development and impedes children’s education in public school.

Such promising directions and trends that determine fundamental and applied approaches to the study and overcoming of speech disorders in the future are, in our opinion, the following:

- in-depth and differentiated development of a medical-psychological-pedagogical approach to the diagnosis and correction of speech disorders based on the study of physiological, psychophysiological, psychological mechanisms of speech pathology and their clinical manifestations in the structure of severe speech disorders;

— a multidimensional study of the psychological characteristics of children and adults with speech pathology from the standpoint of a systematic approach, ensuring the interaction of speech disorders with the psychological characteristics of the individual;

— development of a neuropsychological approach to the study and correction of speech disorders, both in adults and in children with local brain lesions;

— improving the pedagogical aspect of speech therapy, creating new technologies, including computer ones, for the correction of oral and written speech disorders;

— study of the complex structure of a speech defect in combination with sensory and intellectual impairments;

— development of problems of prevention and speech therapy for young children;

- to coordinate the activities of specialists, an extensive network of institutions where speech therapy assistance is provided to children with developmental disorders, create an association of special teachers (speech therapists, teachers of the deaf, oligophrenopedagogues, typhlopedagogues);

— hold a Republican conference on special and inclusive education once every two years.

In this theoretical study and analysis of problems in the field of speech therapy abroad in our republic, we consider it necessary to name and present the names of leading Russian scientists in the field of speech therapy, constituting a galaxy of classics of science, as well as modern researchers who have made significant contributions to solving many scientific issues. However, it is, of course, not possible to collect materials about all the worthy ones and be represented here.

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